

THE VIEW OF PREGNANT WOMEN ON THE QUALITY OF MODERN ANTENATAL CARE

Bekbaulieva Gulistan Nietbaevna

Abduraimova Gulzoda Abduvalievna

Razzakova Nilufar Saidakhmatovna

Tashkent Medical Academy Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: In the Republic of Uzbekistan, thanks to the measures taken since 2005 to introduce new principles of perinatal care, due to the creation of perinatal centers in the administrative territories, there has been a significant decrease in the perinatal mortality rate in general.

Keywords: women, pregnant, antenatal, satisfaction.

Introduction. Meanwhile, in spite of the decrease in the maternal mortality rate, its periodic rise is observed, and yet this indicator still remains similar to the structure of developing countries. The study of the causes of MS according to the literature revealed defects in the work of primary health care [1,3].

One of the tools for maintaining and strengthening the health of the population is to improve the quality of medical care at the level of primary health care. As you know, patient satisfaction with medical care is an integral part of the quality assurance process and customer feedback can improve the provision of medical services [2, 5; 4]. In this regard, in order to find ways to further improve the demographic indicators, we studied the satisfaction of pregnant women with the antenatal care provided to them.

Purpose of the work: assessment of the antenatal care provided from the point of view of pregnant women.

Materials and research methods. With the help of a special questionnaire developed by us, based on the WHO questionnaire, we studied the satisfaction of 1348 pregnant women with antenatal care provided to them, who were registered for pregnancy in the family polyclinic №30 in Tashkent for 2016-2018.

The comparative characteristics of antenatal care in the studied time intervals are presented in the form of extensive indicators with the determination of the degree of reliability of differences in the value of the Student's coefficient: reliable was considered at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results and discussion. The age of the surveyed ranged from 17 to 45 years and averaged 27.9 ± 0.13 years. In particular, the bulk (more than $\frac{2}{3}$) were women aged 20-29 years ($67.2 \pm 1.6\%$), which corresponds to the optimal age of childbirth. Every fifth woman was between the ages of 30-34, only $6.6 \pm 1.4\%$ of women were older than 35, and even fewer were young, up to 20 years of age ($3.9 \pm 2.7\%$).

According to the ethnic composition, the overwhelming majority of pregnant women were Uzbek ($81.8 \pm 1.16\%$), Russians accounted for $12.8 \pm 2.5\%$ and $5.4 \pm 2.6\%$ were representatives of other nationalities.

As the most important element of the medical activity of pregnant women, their education and profession can be considered. The study of the level of education showed that the overwhelming majority of women ($85.6 \pm 1.0\%$) had secondary specialized or secondary education, only $11.4 \pm 2.6\%$ had completed higher education, and the remaining $3 \pm 2.6\%$ had incomplete higher education.

Among the respondents, $71.9 \pm 1.4\%$ were housewives, $24.6 \pm 2.4\%$ were workers, and only $3.6 \pm 2.7\%$ were white-collar workers.

When analyzing the obstetric anamnesis of the respondents, it turned out that $\frac{1}{3}$ were women with the first and second pregnancy ($32.6 \pm 2.2\%$ and $30.0 \pm 2.3\%$, respectively). Attention is drawn to the presence of the fourth and fifth pregnancies in $14.7 \pm 2.5\%$ of the respondents. However, the estimated fourth and fifth births were only $4.4 \pm 2.7\%$. Consequently, more than $10.0 \pm 2.5\%$ of women had a history of spontaneous miscarriages.

At the time of the survey, half of the pregnant women surveyed were for more than 16 weeks ($50.1 \pm 1.9\%$), while about $\frac{1}{3}$ of the respondents were for more than 25 weeks, which makes it possible to obtain more information about the quality of antenatal care provided.

One of the quality indicators of work on antenatal care is the early registration of pregnant women on the "D" record (up to 12 weeks). The analysis showed that of all the respondents, only half ($52.0 \pm 1.9\%$) registered for "D" registration within a period of up to 12 weeks. At the same time, $48.0 \pm 2.0\%$ of pregnant women were registered later than 12 weeks. It should be especially noted that $7.0 \pm 2.6\%$ of pregnant women were registered for more than 30 weeks, which indicates the weak work of the outpatient service in active home-based patronage and early detection of pregnant women.

The weak work of the patronage service is also confirmed by the fact that to the question: "Were you registered for pregnancy as a result of patronage by a health worker, or did you go to the clinic yourself?", More than of the respondents ($64.7 \pm 1.6\%$) answered that they themselves turned to a doctor and only $\frac{1}{3}$ ($35.3 \pm 2.2\%$) of

pregnant women were registered as a result of household patronage. This fact confirms once again that the late registration of women on the "D" registration for pregnancy largely depends on the weak work of the patronage service for the early detection and registration of pregnant women on the "D" registration. It should be noted that pregnant women themselves actively attend scheduled examinations. Thus, the bulk (73.8 ± 1.4%) of the surveyed women answered that they always come for a scheduled regular examination by a doctor on the appointed date.

An analysis of the women we interviewed showed that the overwhelming majority of them are dissatisfied with the antenatal care provided to them. To find out the reasons for the dissatisfaction of the respondents, we studied the defects in the organizational work of the antenatal care service. Thus, 65.7 ± 1.2% of women surveyed are not satisfied with the number of antenatal visits (7 times), and the overwhelming majority of them (89.1 ± 1.04%) believe that the frequency of visits should be increased, and only 10.9 ± 1.04% want to reduce the number of visits.

Taking into account the desire of pregnant women to increase the frequency of visits, the discipline of pregnant women in the appointment of a doctor's visits was studied. It turned out that the bulk of the respondents visited the doctor at the appointed time (73.8 ± 1.2% of pregnant women). This fact testifies to the increase in the medical culture of women thanks to the large-scale state policy of our country. However, 26.2 ± 1.2% of women visit a doctor at will, regardless of the appointed date.

We found out why women would like to increase the frequency of visits. All of them related to improving the quality of antenatal care. Thus, the majority of respondents (59.3 ± 1.7%) who want to increase the frequency of visits believe that the quality of examination and observation will improve, 18.6 ± 1.3% indicated that more attentive and detailed consultations would be provided, 7, 9 ± 0.9% believe that additional visits will make it possible to prepare a woman for childbirth, and 4.6 ± 0.7%, that this will prevent complications of pregnancy and childbirth, and 9.6 ±

Figure 1. Reasons for the desire of respondents to increase the frequency of visits (in%).

Of all the respondents, the majority of women ($62.2 \pm 1.3\%$) believe that the frequency of visits should be 1 time per month, $29.7 \pm 1.2\%$ of them believe that 2 visits per month are necessary, and $6.7 \pm 0.7\%$ - once a week. Only $1.0 \pm 0.07\%$ of the respondents indicated that one visit every 3 months is enough.

At the same time, it is interesting to note that $37.8 \pm 4.8\%$ of respondents who are satisfied with the standard number of doctor visits (7 times during pregnancy), nevertheless, would like the doctor to consult them at least 2 times a month. including $16.2 \pm 4.2\%$ - every week, which would increase the total number of visits to 30 or more times. It is noteworthy that among women who are not satisfied with the standard number of doctor visits, $33.9 \pm 1.6\%$ also believe that it is necessary to visit a doctor 2 times a month, and another $1.7 \pm 0.4\%$ indicated weekly visit doctor. It should be noted that women who regularly and on time come to see a doctor more often would like to increase the number of doctor's consultations during pregnancy ($37.5 \pm 1.5\%$). And even $32.2 \pm 2.5\%$ of pregnant women who do not comply with the turnout period also indicate 2 or more visits per month.

Among all respondents, almost $\frac{2}{3}$ ($61.9 \pm 1.3\%$) indicated that the number of visits to the doctor was actually less than they expected, and only a third of the respondents believed that the number of visits was in line with the expected. At the same time, among those who consider the standard number of visits sufficient, the majority ($62.3 \pm 2.25\%$) noted that their actual number of visits to the doctor was the same as expected, while the absolute majority ($77, 2 \pm 1.4\%$) of those who were not satisfied with the standard number of visits noted that the number of examinations by

their doctor was less than expected and the interval between examinations was too long ($58.1 \pm 1.6\%$). Even among those women who are satisfied with the standard number of visits to the doctor, $32.7 \pm 2.2\%$ also believe that their number of visits was less than they would like, and the interval between them was too large ($27.1 \pm 2, 0\%$ women). The obtained differences of the given indicators are reliable with the probability of an erroneous prediction equal to $p < 0.0001$.

When studying the relationship between the discipline of patients and assessing the real number of visits to a doctor by pregnant women and the interval between examinations, it was found that among all women who carefully and did not regularly visit a doctor, a significantly larger percentage believed that the number of real visits was less than their expectations ($58.2 \pm 1.6\%$ and $72.5 \pm 2.4\%$) and the interval between them was large ($43.0 \pm 1.6\%$ and $60.1 \pm 2.6\%$). Nevertheless, among women who visited a doctor accurately and on time, there were significantly more of those who considered real visits and the interval between them normal ($36.9 \pm 1.5\%$ and $44.8 \pm 1.6\%$ versus $21, 0 \pm 2.2\%$ and 24.9 ± 2.3 in non-disciplined women, $p < 0.0001$).

Thus, the above data show that the standard number of doctor visits during pregnancy, in the opinion of women, requires an upward adjustment.

Of no small importance in assessing the quality of antenatal care is the organization of the doctor's work from the patient's point of view. An analysis of the waiting time for a doctor's appointment showed that $61.7 \pm 1.3\%$ of pregnant women were not satisfied with it. The respondents' dissatisfaction was associated with the length of waiting for an appointment at a medical institution. As it turned out, only half of all respondents ($49.4 \pm 1.3\%$) waited up to 30 minutes for an appointment, $36.9 \pm 1.3\%$ of pregnant women had to wait from 30 minutes to 1 hour, and $8.3 \pm 0.76\%$ - more than 1 hour. It is important to note that of those patients who did not comply with the turn-out time, more than half ($57.5 \pm 2.6\%$) waited for an appointment for more than 30 minutes, while among disciplined women there were only $40.6 \pm 1.5\%$ of such patients, $p < 0.0001$.

Considering that pregnant women spend quite a long time waiting for a doctor's appointment, we analyzed how much time the doctor spends on examination. It turned out that in $90.8 \pm 0.78\%$ of patients the doctor spent up to 30 minutes for examination and consultation, and among those who were satisfied with the waiting time for an appointment, there were $83.7 \pm 1.6\%$, and among those who were not satisfied waiting time was $95.1 \pm 0.7\%$, $p < 0.0001$.

To the question "Do you think it is necessary to increase or decrease the doctor's time for your examination and consultation?", The following data were

received. Among those patients who were treated by the doctor for up to 30 minutes, $87.9 \pm 0.9\%$ believed that this time was enough, but $11.7 \pm 0.9\%$ preferred to increase the time of appointment. Among those who received a doctor for more than 30 minutes, $93.6 \pm 2.2\%$ of pregnant women are satisfied with the time of appointment, and $4.8 \pm 1.9\%$ want to increase it. The difference in indicators is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The need to slightly reduce the time of admission was noted by a very small number of patients (0.5% of all respondents).

Conclusions: Thus, the study of the opinion of pregnant women about the quality of antenatal care showed:

1. Not all pregnant women are satisfied with the antenatal care provided to them, in particular, most of them are not satisfied with the established standard number of visits during pregnancy, believing that they should be increased as it will lead to an improvement in the quality of examination and observation. Consequently, the standard number of antenatal doctor visits during pregnancy, in the opinion of women, needs to be adjusted upward.

2. Pregnant women lose a very long time waiting for a doctor's appointment and require measures to regulate the waiting time for a doctor's appointment.

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